

Deliverable D3.2.1

Workpackage WP3

Deposit of all the reference strains within microbial collections considered as “reference collections”

Responsible Partner: INRAE

Contributing partners: IP, DTU, PIWET, IZSLER, SSI, IZSAM, SLV, SVA, WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Deposit of reference strains within microbial reference centers. Dec,2022

The following table gives the number of strains in the CARE collection and their status in the mBRCs.

Strains Status	Strain number
pending	74
Campylobacter coli	1
Campylobacter jejuni	2
Listeria monocytogenes	52
Salmonella enterica	19
MDA signed	1
Bacillus cereus	1
received in BRCs	345
Bacillus cereus	13
Bacillus mycoides	3
Bacillus paranthracis	1
Bacillus toyonensis	2
Campylobacter coli	24
Campylobacter fetus	1
Campylobacter jejuni	61
Campylobacter lanienae	1
Campylobacter lari	1
Escherichia coli	38
Listeria innocua	1
Listeria monocytogenes	82
Listeria welshimeri	1
Salmonella bongori	1
Salmonella enterica	81
Staphylococcus aureus	25
Staphylococcus hyicus	2
Yersinia enterocolitica	7
Open to diffusion	185
Mammaliicoccus sciuri	2
Salmonella enterica	140
Staphylococcus aureus	20

Staphylococcus epidermidis	1
Yersinia enterocolitica	17
Yersinia pseudotuberculosis	5
Total strain in CARE collection Dec 2022	605

The content of the CARE collection can be accessed at the Public CARE collection website: <https://cirmbp.bio-aware.com/> and the current strain status can be obtained by asking the mBRC.